

Kinetic Study of the Oxidation of (—) Ethyl Lactate by Chromium (VI)

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A kinetic study of oxidation of optically active (—) ethyl lactate by chromic acid is made. The rate is proportional to the first power of concentration of HCrO_4^- , of ester and of H^+ ions, respectively. The values of heat of activation, the entropy of activation and of free energy of activation for the reaction are 16 k. cal., -14 e. u. and 20382 cal respectively. The results are explained on the basis of steric hindrance.

BAKORE and Narain¹ have studied the chromic acid oxidation of lactic, malic, mandelic, glycolic and tartaric acid. The chromic acid oxidation of ethyl esters of mandelic acid has been studied, by Sundaram and Venkatasubramanian². The slow rate of oxidation of this ester as compared with the rate of oxidation of the corresponding alcohol leads them to suggest the influence of a steric factor on reaction rates. If a steric factor is responsible for the observed reaction rates, then the rates of the optically active esters must also be different. A kinetic study of the chromic acid oxidation of (—) ethyl lactate was undertaken with a view to see the effect of steric factor on the reaction rates of ester especially when it is optically active.

Experimental

Material: Chromic acid solutions were prepared from 'AnalaR' potassium dichromate. Glacial acetic acid was distilled over CrO_3 to remove any reducing impurity present. (—) Ethyl lactate obtained from C. H. Boehringer-Sohn Ingelheim Am Rhein (Germany) was used in the present investigation. This compound has the following physical properties: b.p. $155^\circ/69-70/36$ mm; D^{20} : 1.03 $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -10.33$ and n_D^{20} : 1.41. MnSO_4 and other reagent used were chemically pure.

Kinetic measurements: The experiments were carried out at a constant temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The solvent used was 50% glacial acetic acid. The reactants were brought to thermostat temperature and then transferred to bottles previously brought to thermostat temperature. Then the dichromate solution was added. Zero time was taken as the instant when half of the dichromate solution was in the bottle. Aliquots were withdrawn at known interval of time and the gross concentration of chromium was estimated by the iodometric method, taking precaution to minimize oxidation by air³.

Results

Rate laws: When concentrations of ester and the hydrogen ions are kept high compared to that of chromium (VI), the rate at which chromium (VI) disappears follows the first order rate law. Bakore and Narain⁴

have shown that for the concentration of Cr (VI) used for the experiments, practically the whole of chromium (VI) exists as HCrO_4^- . The order of reactions with respect to HCrO_4^- is, therefore, one.

The order with respect to ester is also one and order with respect to hydrogen ions is also one.

Effect of manganese ions on the rate:

Addition of manganese (II) decreases the rate of oxidation. It changes from $4.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min.}^{-1}$ to $3.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min.}^{-1}$ at 32° under the condition when ester concentration is $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, Cr(VI) concentration is $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, H^+ ion concentration 1.2 mole/litre and Mn (II) ion concentration 5×10^{-3} mole/litre in 1:1 (v/v) acetic acid water mixture.

The specific rates at various temperatures calculated from the observed first order rate constant by the relation

$$\text{Specific rate (K)} = \frac{K_1}{(\text{H}^+) (\text{Ester})} \text{ litre}^2 \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

The Arrhenius equation is found to be valid. The energy of activation (ΔE) was calculated to be 16.0 kcal/mole.

This value was used to estimate the pZ, factor from the relation

$$k (\text{Specific rate}) = pZ e^{-E/RT}$$

The average value of pZ works out to be $8.0 \times 10^9 \text{ litre}^2 \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. The entropy of activation $\Delta S^\ddagger$ was obtained from the pZ factor from the relation

$$pZ = 10^{13} e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R}$$

The entropy of activation, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ works out to be -14 e.u. The free energy of activation calculated from the data obtained for the oxidation of (—) ethyl lactate system by chromium (VI) at 313° was 20.4 k cal.

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Discussion

Oxidation of the ester of α -hydroxy acid $RCH(OH)COOR'$ with chromic acid gives the corresponding Keto-ester $R.CO.COOR'$. The oxidation is kinetically similar to the oxidation of secondary alcohols⁶ and of hydroxy acids (Bakore and Narain *et al.*). The rate of oxidation for the ester is less than that for the corresponding alcohol, the order being $R' = -COOH > -CH_3 > -COOC_2H_5$.

Sundaram and Venkatasubramanian (*loc. cit.*) have explained this by postulating that in the oxidation of hydroxy-acid $RCH(OH)COOH$, the oxidation involves reaction between $RCH(OH)COO^-$ and $HCrO_4^-$. If it were so, rate outline for the oxidation of $RCH(OH)COOH$ depending on pH would be different from that for alcohols and esters; in fact the oxidation of the hydroxy acid would not be acid catalysed since the the product $[RCH(OH)COO^-][H^+]$ would be constant when $H^+ \gg K_{HA}$ (dissociation constant for the acid). This is contrary to the observation of Bakore and Narain (*loc. cit.*) who observed first order rate dependence on the hydrogen ion concentration. Thus, the mechanism suggested by Sundaram and Venkatasubramanian (*loc. cit.*) is not satisfactory.

Bakore and Jain (*loc. cit.*) have pointed out that the mechanism of oxidation of α -hydroxy acids is probably different from that of alcohol and esters. In case of α -hydroxy acid, there is a possibility that the chromic ester

may form a cyclic anhydride and that this structure enhances the rate of oxidation. Such cyclic anhydrides are not possible in case of secondary alcohols and esters of hydroxy acids. To account for the differences in rates of secondary alcohol $RCH(OH)CH_3$ and the

ester $RCH(OH)COOC_2H_5$, Bakore and Jain (*loc. cit.*) have postulated the participation of neighbouring group. We have utilised the Newman's "rule of six"⁷ to suggest that the ester group hinders the rate of formation of chromic ester and hence that of oxidation.

If steric hindrance is affecting the rate of formation of chromic ester and hence of oxidation, one would expect that the rates of oxidation of racemic ethyl lactate and of (-) ethyl lactate should be different, as is observed by Jha⁸ who found a specific rate constant (k) was of $1.59 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for racemic ethyl lactate at 313°, while for (-) ethyl lactate found by us as $4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 313°. The energy of activation (E), the entropy of activation and the free energy of activation reported in the Jha's⁸ work were $14.0 \pm 1 \text{ k.cals}$, $-22 \pm 3 \text{ e.u.}$ and 20.9 k.cals while in the case of (-) ethyl lactate, they were $16.0 \pm 1 \text{ k.cals}$, $-14.0 \pm 3 \text{ e.u.}$ and 20.4 k.cals respectively. The energy of activation observed for (-) ethyl lactate is comparable to that observed by Jha for racemic ethyl lactate; however, the entropy of activation has a smaller negative value of (-) ethyl lactate. Thus the results reported here lends support to the hypothesis of steric hindrance advanced by us to explain the difference in the rates of esters of hydroxy acids and the corresponding alcohols.

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